

Narcissism As A Predictor Of Obsessive Compulsive Disorder, Perfectionism And Achievement Motivation Among Adults

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Abstract

The present study intended to explore narcissism as a predictor of obsessive compulsive disorder, perfectionism and achievement motivation among adults. 300 participants including both genders, ages ranging from 18 to 45 years were administered Narcissistic Personality Inventory, Yale Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale, Almost Perfect Scale-Revised, and Achievement Motivation Scale. Results reveal that reliability coefficients of all the scales were greater than .70 indicating satisfactory internal consistency. Narcissism has significant positive correlation with obsessive compulsive disorder perfectionism and achievement motivation. Furthermore narcissism significantly predicted perfectionism, obsessive compulsive disorder and achievement motivation in all the groups respectively. Findings divulged that males were significantly higher on narcissism and obsessive compulsive disorder as compared to females whereas no gender differences were found on perfectionism and achievement motivation.

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Introduction

Narcissism is an inflated sense of self. Except in the sense of primary narcissism or healthy self-love, narcissism is usually considered a problem in a person's or group's relationships with self and others. Healthy narcissism is a structural truthfulness of the self-achievement of self and object constancy harmonization between the self and the superego and a balance between libidinal and aggressive drives, the ability to receive gratification from others and the drive for impulse expression. Healthy narcissism forms a steady, pragmatic self-interest and mature goals and principles and an ability to form deep object relations. An attribute related to healthy narcissism is the feeling of enormity.

Narcissism and Achievement Motivation

Healthy narcissism is characterized by emphatic behavior of helping their master, is dragged by emotion of lust and envy, and sense of discipline and strength. Individuals with positive sense of self-esteem are autonomous internally, having control over behavior, thoughts, will and emotions [1]. Individuals with healthy narcissism will have the potential to stomach disgrace, desolation and also have the strength to handle distinction, supremacy, they have sense of possession, obligation, gratitude, material self-applause, limitations, strength of tolerance for elucidation, criticism, bombastic fantasies which rendered them productive in terms of achievements, a discipline of strength display, a balance of privilege, a model of mercy and compassion, highly appreciative of devoir, ability to control malice, humiliation, pride, arrogance, and appraisal [2]. As regard their creative, professional or academic achievement is concerned, gifted narcissists with cerebral gift can be productive and can sustain a longer run of achievements. They can translate task and occasions to opportunity and indicate a sense of their superiority [1]. Narcissists are usually eminently successful in business, as business generally fancies those who can wield other individuals.

Narcissism and Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder

People with narcissism and Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD) heed a false-self – a counterfeit psychological structure that corrodes the true-self and take over it. The false-self is concerned completely with the exterior appearance and with the objective of achieving narcissism provisions (sanction, sycophancy, acknowledgement, engrossment and stardom). Such a false-self is uncompromising, vicious and demanding [3].

The behavior of both OCD and narcissist is like a "machines" or "automata". The inner coercion is linked with lack of empathy, inexorableness, and brutality to accomplish goals set by the False-self. The OCD's framed and proclaimed reimburse for the demolishing anxiety which is a product of dearth of self-worth and confidence, and serve excruciating self-doubt and self-criticism. The False-self of the narcissist safeguard him against narcissistic afflictions and help regulating his undulating sense of self-growth. Thus, the narcissists are deficient in the sophistry of the OCD, both though deny absoluteness, and are self-deranged and socially gauche[4,5].

Narcissism and Perfectionism

People belonging to "socially prescribed perfectionism" class take inspiration from peripherally motivated beliefs that struggling to be perfect and being perfect are inevitable for others. People from "socially prescribed perfectionism" class are of the view that others will demand perfection from them and that they will face high criticism if found imperfect [6]. The origin of research in narcissism started from psychopathology, narcissism traits are normal and spread over a wide range of population. In the case of "normal narcissism" this is in particularly true [7]. Raskin and Terry describe normal narcissism as a state that reflects the differences among individuals in showing off their achievements, preoccupation with physical look, a feeling of supremacy, and a feeling of being designated to marked treatment. Some authors are of the belief that we live in the era of entitlement and believe narcissism to be exceedingly prevalent [8].

Narcissism and Gender

An important or fundamental element of narcissism is gender [9]. Males are more narcissistic than female. The gender difference which is seen can be due to difference in self-conceptualization: those males are more individualistic and thus also more narcissistic [10]. Our indigenous culture, values and norms is another important consideration in undertaking this research. Our culture is a collectivistic culture where the level of narcissism different from western cultures as the research evidence shows that in collectivistic culture people are highly valuable but narcissists in even that culture attracts towards the targets who offered the potential for self enhancement. Influences of our culturally rich society upon anxiety, OCD, and narcissism have yet to be found. This study is supposed to offer a reliable of these constructs in terms of our widespread conceptualization of these constructs that may offer a comparison with other societies.

Conceptual Framework

Hypotheses

1. Narcissism will positively predict OCD among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees.
2. Narcissism will positively predict perfectionism among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees.
3. Narcissism will positively predict achievement motivation among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees.
4. Males will be higher on narcissism and OCD among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees.

Sample

The current study was based on cross sectional survey design. The data was collected from different participants over the same period of time. Narcissism was the independent variable of the study whereas OCD, perfectionism and achievement motivation were dependent variables of the study. The sample comprised of 300 participants taken from three different areas of Rawalpindi and Islamabad. The participants were chosen through purposive convenient sampling technique. The sample included males ($n=150$) and females ($n=150$). The sample comprised on university students ($n = 100$), bankers ($n = 100$), and telecom franchise employees($n = 100$). The age range of the sample was 18 to 45 years.

Instruments

The Narcissistic Personality Inventory–16 is a 16-item self-report measure of trait narcissism derived from the NPI-40. The 16 pairs are scored 0 or 1, and the score on the scale is the mean of all the answers. Reported reliability was .72 [11]. The Yale Brown Obsessive Compulsive Rating Scale is a self-rated version. The scale is clinical-rated, 10-item scale, each item rated from 0 (no symptoms) to 4 (extreme symptoms). Reported reliability was .78 [12]. The Almost Perfect Scale-Revised (Slaney et al., 2001) is 23 items scale consists of three subscales: High Standards, Discrepancy, and Order. It is a self-rated version. Reported reliability was .74 to .76 [13]. The Achievement Motivation Scale consists of 32 items have five point Likert format. The scoring weights given to these responses were 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively for positively worded items and 1,2,3,4 and 5 respectively for a negatively worded item. Reported reliability was .74 [14].

Procedure

The researchers organized meetings with the prospective respondents. They visited different universities, different banks and different franchises in this regard to find out the respondents. The researchers gathered the data after building a satisfactory level of rapport with the respondents. The issues of confidentiality and compliance to the ethical standards were given proper consideration. It was explained clearly that the research is being conducted for academic purpose only. After getting the permission, through convenient sampling individuals were chosen for the study. Four standardized scales were administered. Later, they were acknowledged for their willingness to be part of the study. The present study was correlational therefore quantitative data analysis was conducted. SPSS software version 20 was used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics and reliability analysis was computed to see general trends of data and consistency of scores in data. For the examination of hypothesis 1 to hypothesis 3 simple linear regression analysis was applied. Independent sample t test was applied to see gender differences in narcissism, OCD, perfectionism, and achievement motivation among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees (e.g., hypothesis 4).

Results

Table 1

Psychometric properties, Reliability analysis, and Correlation of Narcissism, OCD, Perfectionism and Achievement motivation among University students, Bankers and Telecom franchise employees

Variables	M	SD	Skew	α	R			
1. Narcissism	7.34	1.16	.18	.72	1	2	3	4
2. OCD	32.43	12.27	.21	.71	--	.35**	.36**	.24**
3. Perfectionism	82.63	22.38	.22	.80	--	--	.24**	.42**
4. Achievement motivation	125.77	32.05	.55	.75	--	--	--	.57**

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 1 shows psychometric properties, reliability analysis, and correlation of narcissism, OCD, perfectionism and achievement motivation among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees. The reliability shows that reliability coefficients of all scales were greater than .70 indicating satisfactory internal consistency of the scales. Results of correlation indicates that Narcissism has significant positive correlation with OCD $r(298) = .35$, $p < .01$, perfectionism $r(298) = .36$, $p < .01$, and achievement motivation $r(298) = .24$, $p < .01$.

Table 2

Narcissism as predictor of Perfectionism, OCD, and Achievement motivation among University students, Bankers and Telecom franchise employees

Model	Perfectionism		OCD		Achievement motivation	
	B	95%CI	B	95%CI	B	95%CI
		LL-UL		LL-UL		LL-UL
(Constant)	2.12**	[.34-.21]	13.32**	[1.31-3.11]	35.11**	[2.12-4.43]
Narcissism	.45**		.35**		.62*	
R^2	.521		.422		.316	
F	3.21**		6.42**		8.67**	

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 2 shows narcissism as predictor of perfectionism, OCD, and achievement motivation among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees. Results indicated that narcissism significantly predicted

perfectionism $F(1, 298) = 3.21, p < .01$. The variance explained by model was 52.1%. Results indicated that narcissism significantly predicted OCD $F(1, 298) = 6.42, p < .01$. The variance explained by model was 42.2%. Moreover, results indicated that narcissism significantly predicted achievement motivation $F(1, 298) = 8.67, p < .01$. The variance explained by model was 31.6%.

Table 3

Gender differences in Narcissism, OCD, Perfectionism, and Achievement motivation among University students, Bankers and telecom Franchise employees

Variables	Male (n = 150)		Female (n = 150)		t(298)	p	95% CI		Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
Narcissism	8.21	1.97	6.99	1.12	2.39	.01	.33	.15	.50
OCD	33.87	14.15	30.06	10.32	3.50	.01	.17	1.44	.39
Perfectionism	84.01	23.21	78.32	18.22	1.01	.24	.02	-1.31	.29
Achievement motivation	124.75	32.02	121.80	30.01	.24	.85	.31	-.13	.24

Table 3 shows gender differences in narcissism, OCD, perfectionism and achievement motivation among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees. Results indicated that males were significantly higher on narcissism $t(298) = 2.39, p < .05$, and OCD $t(298) = 3.50, p < .01$, compared to females. No gender differences were found on perfectionism and achievement motivation.

Discussion

The study explored the narcissism as a predictor of OCD, perfectionism and achievement motivation among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees. The demographic differences in narcissism as a predictor of OCD, perfectionism and achievement motivation were also explored during the course of research. A sample of 300 university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees were collected in equal proportion and was taken from different institutions of Rawalpindi and Islamabad. The alpha reliability indicated that all scales were internally consistent and reliable for further use. Finally the hypotheses were tested by using these reliable and valid scales.

The 1st hypothesis stated that narcissism will predict OCD. The hypothesis of the study was supported by results. Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD) is characterized by invasive, nervousness inducing thoughts (obsessions) which the individual efforts to dismiss through monotonous or ceremonial actions (compulsions), which can be either observable behaviors or mental processes [15]. In terms of personality, Obsessive-Compulsive Individuals tend to exhibit a preoccupation with tidiness and fastidiousness at the expenditure of efficiency, directness and flexibility [16].

The 2nd hypothesis stated that narcissism will predict perfectionism. The hypothesis of the study was supported by results. Narcissism is also form of perfectionism that is basically the perception of one's self. A narcissistic person often has perceived faultless self-image and that is why he/she experienced sense of grandiosity with entrenched in traumatic damages [17]. Narcissists are basically pseudo-perfectionists and they want to get attention by other people and make such circumstances to gain more attention. Such types of actions help them to make their grandiose and idealized self-image. However if there are some hurdles to get desired outcomes they indulges in different types of psychopathology [18].

The 3rd hypothesis stated that narcissism will predict achievement motivation. The hypothesis was accepted by the results. It was found that narcissistic are more sense of grandiose, otiose and self-exaggerating [7]. They want to receive courtesy and respect for the accomplishment of their goals [19]. They also make specific uphold of their physique [20]. These activities oriented to the achievements motivations in routine. Carpenter (2012) found that the choice of topics by narcissist in Facebook use can be driven to updated status continuously to gain exaggerated self-image. These findings indicated positive relation between narcissism with the updating of one's status and posting more self-endorsing subjects [21].

Gender differences were explored in study variables. Hypothesis 4 that males will be higher on narcissism, OCD, perfectionism and achievement motivation compared to females was partially supported. Males are more narcissistic than females might be because of job requirements or they have developed these trends during the service career and now have become an integral part of their personality. Gender difference was found as an important indicator of narcissism [22]. The research findings also examined gender differences and have validated the findings of present research [23].

Results show that males were significantly high on OCD supported by few researchers investigated that either OCD is affected by gender or not. A meta-analysis was conducted which revealed higher level of OCD in males as compared to females because males are more prone to early onset of indications and long-lasting sequence of the disorder, larger social injury, and more sexual-religious and aggressive symptoms. However on the other hand females extant more adulteration/spring-cleaning symptoms and larger co morbidity with eating and impulse-control disorders. Heredity and family related researches also focus the important role of gender in the progression of OCD [24].

They may appear warm and ingratiating but beneath this façade there is a lack of genuine empathy. They are less concerned with meeting customer needs or generating business than with winning approval and admiration for personal attributes. Such self-absorption stifles the flow of vital information, prevents the narcissist from assuming the role of problem-solver and renders him/her less useful to the customer. Since prior research has shown that the top sales performers are adept at recognizing and satisfying their customers' needs [e.g., 25, 26], narcissism should have a negative effect on bank employees.

Conclusion

The study investigated narcissism as a predictor of OCD, perfectionism and achievement motivation among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees. Another objective was to find out the role of the demographic variables in narcissism as a predictor of OCD, perfectionism and achievement motivation. It can be concluded by findings that narcissism predicted of OCD, perfectionism and achievement motivation among university students, bankers and telecom franchise employees. Gender differences revealed that males are more narcissists and have higher level of OCD as compared to females.

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